

From Keynes to Distinctiveness – Triangulation and Evaluation in Computational Literary Studies

Julian Schröter, Keli Du, Julia Dudar, Cora Rok and Christof Schöch

Published by De Gruyter, November 6, 2021.

From the journal *Journal of Literary Theory* 15 (1-2): 81–108.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/jlt-2021-2011>.

(This is a post-review, authors' version of the article not typeset by the publisher.)

Abstract

There is a set of statistical measures developed mostly in corpus and computational linguistics and information retrieval, known as keyness measures, which are generally expected to detect textual features that account for differences between two texts or groups of texts. These measures are based on the frequency, distribution, or dispersion of words (or other features). Searching for relevant differences or similarities between two text groups is also an activity that is characteristic of traditional literary studies, whenever two authors, two periods in the work of one author, two historical periods or two literary genres are to be compared. Therefore, applying quantitative procedures in order to search for differences seems to be promising in the field of computational literary studies as it allows to analyze large corpora and to base historical hypotheses on differences between authors, genres and periods on larger empirical evidence. However, applying quantitative procedures in order to answer questions relevant to literary studies in many cases raises methodological problems, which have been discussed on a more general level in the context of integrating or triangulating quantitative and qualitative methods in mixed methods research of the social sciences. This paper aims to solve these methodological issues concretely for the concept of distinctiveness and thus to lay the methodological foundation permitting to operationalize quantitative procedures in order to use them not only as rough exploratory tools, but in a hermeneutically meaningful way for research in literary studies.

Based on a structural definition of potential candidate measures for analyzing distinctiveness in the first section, we offer a systematic description of the issue of integrating quantitative procedures into a hermeneutically meaningful understanding of distinctiveness by distinguishing its epistemological

from the methodological perspective. The second section develops a systematic strategy to solve the methodological side of this issue based on a critical reconstruction of the widespread non-integrative strategy in research on keyness measures that can be traced back to Rudolf Carnap's model of explication. We demonstrate that it is, in the first instance, mandatory to gain a comprehensive qualitative understanding of the actual task. We show that Carnap's model of explication suffers from a shortcoming that consists in ignoring the need for a systematic comparison of what he calls the explicatum and the explicandum. Only if there is a method of systematic comparison, the next task, namely that of evaluation can be addressed, which verifies whether the output of a quantitative procedure corresponds to the qualitative expectation that must be clarified in advance. We claim that evaluation is necessary for integrating quantitative procedures to a qualitative understanding of distinctiveness. Our reconstruction shows that both steps are usually skipped in empirical research on keyness measures that are the most important point of reference for the development of a measure of distinctiveness. Evaluation, which in turn requires thorough explication and conceptual clarification, needs to be employed to verify this relation.

In the third section we offer a qualitative clarification of the concept of distinctiveness by spanning a three-dimensional conceptual space. This flexible framework takes into account that there is no single and proper concept of distinctiveness but rather a field of possible meanings depending on research interest, theoretical framework, and access to the perceptibility or salience of textual features. Therefore, we shall, instead of stipulating any narrow and strict definition, take into account that each of these aspects – interest, theoretical framework, and access to perceptibility – represents one dimension of the heuristic space of possible uses of the concept of distinctiveness.

The fourth section discusses two possible strategies of operationalization and evaluation that we consider to be complementary to the previously provided clarification, and that complete the task of establishing a candidate measure successfully as a measure of distinctiveness in a qualitatively ambitious sense. We demonstrate that two different general strategies are worth considering, depending on the respective notion of distinctiveness and the interest as elaborated in the third section. If the interest is merely taxonomic, classification tasks based on multi-class supervised machine learning are sufficient. If the interest is aesthetic, more complex and intricate evaluation strategies are required, which have to rely on a thorough conceptual clarification of the concept of distinctiveness, in particular on the idea of salience or perceptibility. The challenge here is to correlate perceivable complex features of texts such as plot, theme (aboutness), style, form, or roles and constellation of fictional characters with

the unperceived frequency and distribution of word features that are calculated by candidate measures of distinctiveness. Existing research did not clarify, so far, how to correlate such complex features with individual word features.

The paper concludes with a general reflection on the possibility of mixed methods research for computational literary studies in terms of explanatory power and exploratory use. As our strategy of combining explication and evaluation shows, integration should be understood as a strategy of combining two different perspectives on the object area: in our evaluation scenarios, that of empirical reader response and that of a specific quantitative procedure. This does not imply that measures of distinctiveness, which proved to reach explanatory power in one qualitative aspect, should be supposed to be successful in all fields of research. As long as evaluation is omitted, candidate measures of distinctiveness lack explanatory power and are limited to exploratory use. In contrast with a skepticism that has sometimes been expressed from literary scholars with regard to the relevance of computational literary studies on proper issues of the humanities, we believe that integrating computational methods into hermeneutic literary studies can be achieved in a way that reaches higher explanatory power than the usual exploratory use of keyness measures, but it can only be achieved individually for concrete tasks and not once and for all based on a general theoretical demonstration.

Keywords: [computational literary studies](#); [distinctiveness](#); [genre theory](#); [triangulation](#); [explication](#); [evaluation](#); [genre](#); [keyness](#)

1 Introduction

This essay aims at a holistic explication of the concept of distinctiveness in order to develop a quantitative operationalization of its qualitative meaning which can be applied in computational literary studies. The reason why we consider this explication to be essential to the methodology of computational literary studies in particular and to literary theory in general is twofold: Firstly, searching for distinctive features is crucial for philological research when similarities and differences between two or more genres, periods, authors, works etc. are investigated. Commonly, we compare two or more categories such as genres or periods with reference to typical, characteristic, differentiating, or specific features – the latter often in the scholastic sense of *differentia specifica*, which is canonical to genre theory (Fricke 2010). Our preliminary understanding of distinctiveness encompasses all these aspects. For this reason, a more precise explication of the concept should not start with a strict and narrow definition of the term which focuses on one of its possible meanings (for example that of *differentia specifica*), but

rather with a logical analysis of the common ground shared by all the mentioned predicates, which put two or more categories into opposition. Such practices of opposing categories by means of distinctive features are constitutive of literary studies, but they have only in parts been conceptualized so far (Klimek/Müller 2015). Secondly, analyzing distinctiveness has a long tradition in quantitative research. In this tradition of corpus and more recently of computer linguistics, a series of mathematical procedures, which are usually called ›keyness measures‹, has been developed (cf. Scott (1997); Egbert/Biber 2019). Occasionally, these procedures were used for an ›analysis of distinctiveness‹ (Paquot/Bestgen 2009; Kilgarriff 2001; and Gabrielatos 2018). We can thus articulate our general aim in more concrete terms: it is the task of this paper to clarify whether these statistical measures are suitable to detect distinctive features in a qualitatively ambitious sense of distinctiveness.

We start with a preliminary definition of keyness measures. By keyness measure we mean functions of a specific structure. These functions f take three parameters: two texts or text corpora A and B , and the frequency, distribution, or dispersion of the occurrences of a feature w in these texts. In keyword analysis, this feature is usually (but not necessarily) a lemmatized word type (Gabrielatos 2018). For analyzing distinctiveness, it can also be a character or word n -gram, a part-of-speech-tag (POS-tag), or a more aggregated construction such as a topic in topic modeling.¹ Although the choice of a different type of feature can lead to different problems in detail or can shift problems to another level, the general conceptual issue remains independent of the type of features. For simplicity’s sake, we are operating only with word features but will return to problems of mediating different types of features in the fourth section of this paper. In a non-mathematical, structuralist notation, keyness measures have the following form:

$$f(w \mid A, B) = (w : A) :: (w : B)$$

The relations $:$ and $::$ are placeholders for mathematical operations: The relation $:$ within the brackets is based on calculating the frequency, distribution, or dispersion of w in A and B . It is the same type of operation in both brackets. The placeholder $::$ between the brackets often consists of a statistical test, which accounts for the statistical significance of the difference between w in A and w in B . This could, for example, be a chi-squared or log-likelihood ratio test in the case of frequencies or a t-test or Wilcoxon test in the case of distributions, or a simpler calculation, e.g., the ratio of relative frequencies or the subtraction of document proportions, which account in a more or less sophisticated way for the effect

¹ Stamatatos (2009) offers a survey of possible features for authorship attribution tasks, which can, in principle, also be used in scenarios of analyzing distinctiveness.

size of this difference. The whole function then returns a numeric value which is interpreted in the following way: the larger the function value, the more strongly feature w accounts for the difference between A and B . In terms of keyness, this means: the larger the value, the more strongly w is key to A and not to B (or vice versa, depending on the configuration of the function).

Based on this structural delineation, we can justify why we expect these measures to be candidates for measuring distinctiveness. Whether or not any specific measure is capable of detecting keyness in a qualitatively meaningful sense is not the objective of this paper. By ›keyness measure‹, we do not refer to any qualitative meaning of ›keyness‹ but to the measures we defined in the preceding section. Hence, we do not address qualitative concepts of keyness, such as the sociolinguistic tradition of keyword analysis, which can be traced back to Firth (1935), Williams (1983) or Schmidt-Hidding (1963).² One can see that the general structure of the technical procedure matches our initial understanding of distinctiveness as a predicate of features of objects. It is a ternary predicate with the feature w in the subject position: ›feature w is more or less distinctive to category A when compared to category B .‹ Here, a difference between the use of the terms ›keyness‹ and ›distinctiveness‹ on the level of their logical syntax comes into play: Whereas distinctiveness emphasizes a difference between two equally relevant objects A and B , the syntax of keyness emphasizes the importance of a feature to only one main subject (› w is key to A ‹), with the second corpus B being of interest only as a comparison corpus. Consequently, in most cases of keyness research in corpus linguistics, B is constructed as a large corpus representative of the general use of language. Another difference concerns the categorical interest in claims on distinctiveness. When we claim that w is key to A (when compared to B), A and B can represent either individual entities (for example two literary works) or groups of texts (for example two literary genres). When we claim that w is distinctive to A compared to B , A and B represent two categories. In this case, we claim that w is a feature that allows us (either alone or, more typically, in conjunction with other, similarly distinctive features) to identify a specific document D as an instance of category A and not of category B . Hence, the notion of distinctiveness is more relevant than that of keyness for our purposes.

With this initial clarification, we are now able to specify the main issue of this paper. Up to here, any name such as ›keyness‹ or ›distinctiveness‹ is, as a mere designator of functions, empty from a qualitative perspective. Nevertheless, each name raises specific expectations. Whereas the metaphor of keyness raises expectations with regard to the qualitative impact of a feature to an object, the notion of

² For recent discussions of the qualitative meaning of ›keyness‹ in relation to quantitative ›key-word analysis‹ in linguistics, cf. Stubbs (2010) and Gabrielatos (2018).

distinctiveness raises expectations regarding the quality of the difference between two categories. However, the mere act of designating a specific quantitative procedure as a ›measure of keyness‹ or a ›measure of distinctiveness‹ does not guarantee that this procedure will give any insight into a qualitatively ambitious understanding of distinctiveness or keyness. We call this the epistemic gap between the output of a quantitative procedure and a qualitative expectation. This gap, which is well known in the social sciences and especially in the field of mixed methods research surrounding discussions on integration and triangulation (Hammersley 2008; Flick 2011; Kelle (2017)), can be addressed either from an epistemological or from a methodological perspective. From the epistemological perspective, the question is: Are quantitative and qualitative research dealing with the same world of objects at all or do both fields of research construct their own worlds, which are not interconnected, and which do not refer to the respective other world? Greene (2008) surveys different stances that have been put forward reaching from a purist incommensurability stance (such as Lincoln/Guba 2018) to more conciliatory a-paradigmatic stances. Remarkably, parts of the intense debates of the last years on the relevance of digital humanities research to proper issues of traditional humanities, in particular arguments that reject such relevance in general,³ rest on such epistemological reasoning. Interestingly, the intensity of these debates shows that scholars of computational literary studies in large parts aim at contributing to proper questions of literary studies (most comprehensively and recently Underwood 2019). So do we, but we will not contribute to the epistemological dimension of this gap, which extends to issues that have to be addressed on the level of metaphysical reasoning. Instead, we will address the epistemic gap from its methodological perspective. In digital humanities research, the methodological dimension of this problem arises for all concepts that have undergone a quantitative and mathematical operationalization, such as ›topic‹ in topic modeling (Blei (2012)), ›style‹ in stylometry (Burrows (2002); Herrmann/Dalen-Oskam/Schöch 2015) and also the concepts of keyness and distinctiveness. The methodological issue of integrating quantitative and qualitative reasoning can also be expressed in terms of validation: As we expect quantitative procedures such as candidate measures of distinctiveness to contribute to qualitative research, the idea of qualitative validation of quantitative procedures has to be developed.

3 Most prominently, Da (2019) caused a stir with her attack against computational literary studies. Although her reasoning is intended to be methodological, parts of her argument are based on epistemologic claims when she maintains that »there is a fundamental mismatch between the statistical tools that are used and the objects to which they are applied.« (601)

2 Explication and the Shortcomings of the Quantitative Paradigm

We will address the methodological perspective of the issue of integrating the quantitative concept of distinctiveness into qualitative research by asking: How do we make sure that a quantitative procedure $f(w \mid A, B)$, as delineated in the first section, returns distinctive features which are distinctive from the point of view of qualitative meaning? In order to understand this methodological perspective in an analytically precise way, we shall describe it in terms of the most prominent non-integrative but reductionist model of transforming qualitative concepts to formalized concepts – Carnap's concept of explication as it is formulated in *Logical Foundations of Probability* (1950). We will exemplify this reductionist relationship between a qualitative concept and one or several quantitative procedures by analyzing the notions of ›keyness‹ and ›keyness measures‹ in research on keyness. Although we are neither interested in the concept of keyness here nor in favoring reductionist transformations, we take our analysis as a starting point for identifying the shortcomings of such transformations and for developing an integrative idea of operationalization.

We start with the most infamous aspect of Carnap's model, namely the idea of a unified formalized science. This idea directly affects the way qualitative concepts are transformed into quantitative procedures. In his own examples, Carnap reveals his disregard of ordinary language terms. Illustratively, he demonstrates how the pre-scientific notion of thermal sensation was replaced by the metrical concept of temperature, as it was formally explicated in physics. Interestingly, the physicist concept of temperature did not only replace the notion of warmth in physics, but also within ordinary language. As Carnap points out, we use sentences such as: ›I thought that it was warmer inside than outside, but the thermometer showed the opposite.‹ For Carnap, the formalized concept and procedure allow for an objective description of the world, whereas the pre-scientific concept proved to be merely subjective, error prone, and thus inferior from an epistemological perspective. When we transfer Carnap's example of thermal sensation and temperature to the relationship between a qualitative notion in humanities research (such as distinctiveness) and a mathematical procedure, there is the danger of devaluing non-mathematized notions as subjective and epistemologically untenable. This is exactly the movement that leads proponents of humanities research to refuse the paradigm of empiricism and logicism as hegemonic. And indeed, the analogy is fallacious because analytical terms in qualitative literary studies can be and often are methodologically regulated rather than merely subjective and pre-scientific. However, the qualitative concept of distinctiveness is unclear, but also – as we will demonstrate – the relation between qualitative concept and quantitative procedure. Based on this initial critique of

Carnap's theory, the task for the next analytical step can be refined. Our analysis, firstly, aims at identifying the Carnapian strategies of reductively replacing qualitative concepts by quantitative procedures in studies on keyness measures. Secondly, it identifies systematic shortcomings and consequences of such reductions; it does so, thirdly, in order to find strategies which overcome this reductionism. Fortunately, Carnap's model gives an implicit and unintended hint on how to overcome the reductionism that it explicitly propagates.

As a strategy of transforming ordinary-language notions into formalized terms, explication starts from the pre-scientific notion, which is called the explicandum. Carnap postulates that the use of the pre-scientific concept has to be clarified in the first step in order to facilitate mutual understanding between scholars (Carnap 1950, 3f.). In the second step, the explicandum that has been clarified in the first instance has to be replaced by a formal procedure. This procedure, which replaces the explicandum, and which can be expressed as a scientific concept, is called explicatum. This substitution of an explicandum by an explicatum is what is nowadays known as operationalization. Carnap enumerates four requirements the explicatum has to satisfy in relation to the explicandum:

1. The explicatum is to be similar to the explicandum in such a way that, in most cases in which the explicandum has so far been used, the explicatum can be used; [...]
2. The characterization of the explicatum, that is, the rules of its use (for instance, in the form of a definition), is to be given in an *exact* form, so as to introduce the explicatum into a well-connected system of scientific concepts.
3. The explicatum is to be a *fruitful* concept, that is, useful for the formulation of many universal statements (empirical laws in the case of a nonlogical concept, logical theorems in the case of a logical concept).
4. The explicatum should be as simple as possible; this means as simple as the more important requirements (1), (2), and (3) permit. (Carnap 1950, 7)

Most contributions to keyness measures can easily be reconstructed along the line of Carnap's model (Scott 1997; 1998; Kilgarriff (2001); Gries (2008); Gabrielatos 2018; Egbert/Biber 2019). These contributions are good on the level of the second and fourth requirements. The shortcomings which affect the issue of integration come from the first and, in a more indirect way, from the third requirement. We will return to the latter at the end of this paper. The problem with the first requirement, that of the similarity between explicatum and explicandum, is that its consideration is typically skipped. While many contributions on keyness measures reflect upon the different usages of

the term ›keyness‹ and its more subjective and intuitive understanding outside statistical and computer-based linguistic or comparative corpus analysis, there is no contribution that takes this more subjective and intuitive understanding as the actual explicandum. It is common to express the concept of keyness in terms of the quantitative procedure itself, for example when Scott defines key word as »a word which occurs with unusual frequency [...] by comparison with a reference corpus« (Scott 1997, 236). Egbert/Biber (2019) offer a short but fruitful clarification of the notion of ›keyness‹ based on differentiating »content-generalisability« and »content-distinctiveness« (Egbert/Biber 2019, 78). However, not even Egbert/Biber’s clarification facilitates comparing the explicandum with the explicatum in a systematic way. Carnap himself addressed the methodological difficulties of clarifying the explicandum and he already anticipated that the preliminary requirement of clarifying the explicandum is often skipped in empirical research. It is, however, a necessary precondition to fulfilling the first requirement. For Carnap, there are no criteria for correct clarification (Carnap 1950, 4). This assumption implies that there is no formalized way to fulfill the first requirement and *a fortiori* to compare the explicandum with the explicatum. At this point, Carnap becomes a victim of his own reductionist theory. His model cuts off the connection between quantitative procedure (explicatum) and the qualitative concept (explicandum) because he misses to define criteria for an evaluation of the explicatum with the explicandum as the touchstone. This connection would, however, be necessary to meet the first requirement.

This logical shortcoming of Carnap’s model can also be found in research on keyness. As we will demonstrate, this shortcoming leads to the characteristic problems of a missing gold standard and hence to merely exploratory use and impressionistic interpretation. Whereas detecting the correct author in undisputed cases is the standard for evaluating the success of a given stylometric procedure in authorship attribution (Stamatatos (2009); Evert et al. 2017), detecting key or distinctive words does not have any comparable condition of success because distinctive or key words are not clearly and externally associated with a text in the way an author is associated with his or her text. The lack of a gold standard leads to a practice in studies on keyness that has already been recognized as unsatisfactory. Whenever the question arises to what extent a specific measure does indeed represent a qualitative meaning of keyness or of distinctiveness, the results are typically interpreted in an ›impressionistic‹ way by contrasting the results of two different metrics in the form of two word lists synoptically and pointing at the intuitively more sensitive word list (Kilgarriff 2001, 248; Egbert/Biber 2019, 96; Paquot/Bestgen 2009, Gabrielatos 2018).⁴ This impressionistic style of interpretation, which affects exploratory approaches

4 »These words [the words of one of both lists] are arguably more typical of fiction writing than academic texts, thus pointing to a limitation of the log-likelihood ratio procedure.« (Paquot/Bestgen 2009, 14)

with post-hoc explanations in general (Gabrielatos 2018; for the notion of explorative analysis cf. Tukey 1977), replaces systematic validation and serves as the strategy to pick out a seemingly best candidate measure. We will return to the implications of using keyness measures in a merely exploratory way at the end of this paper. It is important here to note that impressionistic interpretation is no adequate form of evaluation if Carnap's first requirement shall be met. From a logical perspective, this lack of an evaluation strategy would be unproblematic, if the respective research design was entirely and reductively quantitative so that no return from the quantitative explicatum to the explicandum would be needed. Research on keyness, however, shows, that this return path from the operationalized procedure to a qualitative understanding is difficult to avoid in practice. This entails that Carnap's propagation of a unified science, which equates non-formalized with pre-scientific, subjective, and thus imprecise concepts, is not only misleading but also illusory in the practice of analyzing keyness in linguistic contexts. Irrespective of possible methodological problems that may be characteristic to research within qualitative paradigms, the imprecision of the kind of ›impressionistic interpretation‹ we analyzed in this section is not a consequence of a non-formalized structure of qualitative research, but of a weak qualitative clarification and of a lacking qualitative evaluation standard within a reductive quantitative paradigm. In Linguistics, sophisticated statistical and mathematical evaluation strategies for different candidate measures have been provided by Lijfijt et al. (2014). However, Gries (2008, 427) observed that external evaluation with regard to the qualitative impact of quantitative procedures was lacking, and this still appears to be the case. This shortcoming cannot be overcome from within the quantitative paradigm by means of statistical evaluation alone but only based on an integrative effort of triangulating the qualitative with the quantitative perspective.

As we do not wish to limit ourselves to a merely exploratory use, and because the manual *ad hoc* definition of a gold standard would amount to impressionistic interpretation and hence to a merely exploratory use, a reasonable gold standard must be based on a thorough qualitative clarification of the explicandum. This applies equally to both concepts, that of keyness and that of distinctiveness. As we are interested in the latter concept here, we shall delineate the qualitative concept of distinctiveness in the following section. Proper strategies of evaluation have then to be designed based on a clarification of the explicandum. Hence, clarifying the explicandum and evaluating the explicatum, which are opposite sides of the same coin, are the components of our integrative effort. Combining both sides of that coin is mandatory because we need to know what result we expect to obtain when applying a computational technique.

3 Dimensions of Qualitative Clarification

As any concept, the concept of distinctiveness can be defined in various ways depending on different interests, methods, and theoretical background. Our task here is not to stipulate any specific definition, but to delineate the space of different reasonable, explicable and operationalizable uses of that concept. Different uses imply different expectations regarding the output of an analysis and hence necessitate different evaluation strategies. The space of reasonable definitions can be spanned to three dimensions.

3.1 Taxonomic versus Aesthetic or Historical Categories

The first dimension can be called ›interest in categorization‹: On one pole, there is the aim of a taxonomic system of distinct categories – for example a Linnéan *tableau* of species. In genre theory, constructing systematic taxonomies has for a long time been regarded as the most honorable goal of genre research (Fricke 1981; Duncker 2010; Müller 2010). On the other pole, there is the historical and aesthetic aim of reconstructing categories from the perspective of structural, functional, aesthetic or conceptual history (Voßkamp 1977; Swales 1990; Ryan (1981)). Much effort in literary genre theory has gone into mediating between both poles (Gymnich/Neumann/Nünning 2007, Lamping 2009). On the latter pole, distinctiveness is part of the historical genre semantics that shall be uncovered, and it is regarded as a basic construction principle for the system of literary genres within historical cultures. Recent research has acknowledged that historical genre systems were not coherent, that boundaries between genres were blurred, and that genres were in fact mixed (Hempfer (2010)). The most compelling arguments for the aesthetic relevance of historical genre categories have been put forward by Walton (1970) from a more systematic and by Jauß (1867) from a more historicist perspective. Both claim that it is necessary to take into account categorical expectations expressed by contemporary genre semantics when a literary work shall be interpreted properly. A sense of perfection in a sonata, for example, can only be perceived if the perception is guided by the expectations which are raised by the knowledge of the *sonata allegro* form. Features that are expected and that generate aesthetic experience are called standard features relative to the category a work of art is perceived in (Walton (1970), 337ff.).⁵

5 From the perspective of conceptual analysis within genre theory as well as from the perspective of hermeneutics, this first dimension actually consists of several more basic dimensions. Usually, aesthetic, historical, structural, and functional interest, which are combined here because of their commonalities with regard to evaluation (see section 4), should be separated with regard to their theoretical and methodological framework (Duncker 2010). Moreover, this first dimension is oriented towards genre theory. For comparison of periods and the work of different authors, and further tasks, this dimension may be constructed differently.

The heuristic reason why we compose the first dimension in this way is that the taxonomic interest in its most radical form – a form that is no longer practiced in genre research – has completely different conditions of success than the historical interest in its radical form and therefore requires a radically different sort of evaluation strategy. As computational genre stylistics has a strong tendency towards the axiomatic pole but in most cases also a historical interest, the concept of distinctiveness in computational literary studies has to be specified with regard to its position on this first axis for each concrete case study.

3.2 *Differentia specifica* versus Statistical Categorization

On the second dimension, there is, on one pole of the axis, the strictly logical sense of distinctiveness as ›specific difference‹ according to the scholastic model of *genus proximum* and *differentia specifica*. On the other end, there is a merely relativist understanding of distinctiveness with regard to features that account for identifying objects as instances of a category. For traditional genre theorists and several logicians, the first pole on this axis might be regarded as the proper meaning of distinctiveness (Fricke 2010). It can be defined as follows:

A feature *w* is distinctive to category *A* if its presence in a document *D* is a necessary and sufficient condition for *D* to belong to *A*.⁶

In the classical sense of *differentia specifica*, two objects can be said to be distinct if there is at least one distinctive feature, that is a feature that is necessary and sufficient to *A*. This scholastic notion of distinctiveness is compelling from a logical perspective, but it has lost ground during the last 70 years in genre theory. This has much to do with the historical interest as the second pole in the first dimension. When scholars investigated the actual use of genre concepts in historical or present literary cultures, it became increasingly clear that the scholastic model of *genus proximum* and *differentia specifica* does not fit well with genre concepts as actually practiced in literary culture. For this reason, the strict sense of classification has been replaced by or complemented by Wittgenstein’s theory of family resemblance and of prototype theory (Fishelov 199; Strube 1989; Lamping 2009; Hempfer 2010; Schröter (2019)). Hence, it has become customary to use the notion ›distinctive feature‹ in a less strict sense and more in

⁶ In genre theory, this concept of distinctiveness is presented by Fishelov (1992) and Fricke (1981 and 2010). Sometimes, ›distinctive‹ is used on the level of objects and of categories. For both cases we prefer the predicate ›distinct‹. In several contexts of language use, ›distinctive‹ refers to the behavior of agents or groups to highlight their own otherness, such as the book title *Are Muslims Distinctive* (Fish 2011). For the sake of terminological clarity, we will use the attribute ›distinct‹ only on the level of objects, and ›distinctive‹ only on the level of the features of objects.

the sense of ›typical feature‹. This relativist use of distinctiveness is also at the core of computational literary studies. It can be formulated as follows:

That feature w is distinctive to category A means that, the higher the frequency of w in document D , the higher the probability that D is an instance of A .

Thanks to multivariate statistics, where many, often several thousands of features are counted and where distribution or dispersion can be calculated for all features over all documents in different categories, the combination of several distinctive features in this statistical sense amounts to more or less reliable assignments of documents to categories. This latter statistical sense of distinctiveness is relativist in two respects: Firstly, the basis for calculations is a frequency, a distribution, or a dispersion instead of a binary information regarding the presence or absence of a feature. Secondly, the result of the calculation leads to a probability for a document to belong to a category, rather than to an uncontested binary classification.

In principle, the concept of distinctiveness in the first and the second dimensions can be freely combined. In practice, however, several combinations are prevalent: In scholastic reasoning, for example, the taxonomic interest was built upon the notion of *differentia specifica*. In computational literary studies, we can observe a tendency towards a combination of the taxonomic interest with the relativist and statistical conception of distinctiveness. For this second dimension, an understanding of distinctiveness as *differentia specifica* necessitates completely different analytic methods than the ones required in a frequentist and relative understanding. This is why the position of the concept of distinctiveness to be used in concrete research has to be specified before potential candidate measures are evaluated for detecting distinctive features.

3.3 Perceived and Salient versus Agnostic Features

The third dimension is that of perceived versus agnostic features. By agnostic, we mean ›potentially unperceived‹. On this pole, it is irrelevant whether a distinctive feature is perceived as distinctive by human readers. On the other pole of this third dimension, a feature is distinctive only if it is perceived as distinctive by human readers. Within the hermeneutic interest on the first dimension, all distinctive features must be perceived features. Conversely, the agnostic stance is typical to statistical reasoning and in particular to stylometric authorship attribution. In this field, ›agnostic‹ means that, although singular word occurrences may be perceived, the frequency, distribution, and dispersion of these words do not need to be perceived in their mathematically expressed form. As we have shown in section 3.2, it is this

agnostic frequency, distribution, or dispersion of a feature w that accounts for the distinctiveness in a statistical sense.

The reason why this dimension is crucial for the issue of integration rests on the complex conceptual relationship between distinctiveness and perceptibility, which has strong implications for the matter of evaluation. In psychology and sociolinguistics, a rather strict notion of perceptibility, namely that of ›salience‹, is used synonymously to that of ›distinctiveness‹. In many contributions on keyness measures, the terms ›distinctiveness‹, ›keyness‹, and ›salience‹ are also used interchangeably and without further terminological definition (Gabrielatos 2018). Accordingly, all contributions we discussed in the second section tend to interpret the function values of a keyness measures $f(w \mid A, B) = (w : A) :: (w : B)$ (see first section) in a way that a high value for a feature w in function f means that this feature is strongly salient. Arguably, this interpretation is wrong for all known candidate measures. Functions f featuring log-likelihood ratio or chi-squared tests based on word frequency usually yield high values for the least perceivable word features, in particular for stop words or function words. However, also the zeta-scores of Burrows (2007), which often yield more semantic and therefore ›interesting‹ words than statistical tests based on word frequency, do not automatically yield the most salient features. Thus, there is some kind of dilemma in the use of measures of distinctiveness in computational literary studies: While it is clear that candidate measures f do not reliably return the most salient features, the manner of impressionistic interpretation we discussed in the second section typically includes the tendency to look for ›salient‹ features.

With regard to further clarification of the conceptual relationship between distinctiveness and salience, we start with the meaning of salience in psychology, where it refers to the property of a feature to be prominent and conspicuous in comparison with the surrounding features because of its surprising deviation from contextual expectations in the speech signal (Rácz 2013). At the core of the concept is the idea of a context that regulates expectations.⁷ With regard to our task of explicating the concept of distinctiveness, two basic distinctions will be sufficient in order to configure appropriate evaluation strategies: firstly that between salience based on contextual accordance with aesthetic expectations versus salience based on deviation from contextual expectations, and, secondly the differentiation of levels of complexity of features. Both distinctions are important for all use cases where not only two documents are compared (as in some use cases of key word analysis) but where documents are

7 We believe that more work at the interface of literary theory and computational literary studies should be done on integrating the psychological concept of salience to the the notions of foregrounding, defamiliarization, and the concept of ostranenie in the tradition of Russian Formalism (Šklovskij 1969).

investigated in order to search for distinctive features of categories such as genres, periods or the work of two or more different authors. As for the first dimension of categorical interest, we will discuss the relevance of both distinctions in an exemplary way with regard to genres. Transfer to other types of categories such as periods or author works will have to be done separately.

The first distinction corresponds to that between *Abweichungsästhetik* (aesthetics of deviation) and *Regelpoetik* (poetics of rules). According to aesthetics of deviation, a feature appears to be salient because it marks a deviation from genre expectations as elaborated in section 3.1 for the aesthetic interest (Walton 1970, 337–342). According to a poetics of rules, conversely, a feature can be conspicuous *because* it realizes an expectation which is raised by the category. We do not go into the details of the mutual dependency of both forms of aesthetics (cf. Fricke 1981). We are only interested in the implications of this difference on the notion of distinctiveness. This difference helps to make clear that completely different features can be taken to be salient in the same document by the same reader when different genre expectations are raised or when the stance is reversed from an aesthetics of deviation to expectation according to genre rules (or vice versa). This entails that there is no simple binary relation between a document and the salience of a feature, but a complex relativist relation that should include the category that is expected as well as the form of aesthetic expectation (deviation from versus accordance with expectations). If this relativism is overlooked, ambiguity in the notion of salience cannot be controlled. When we look at the form of the candidate measures that are included by our initial definition in the first section, it is easy to see that these measures do not in their inner structure model the concept of salience based on deviation from contextual, i.e. categorical expectations such as genre expectations.⁸ What these measures can at best be expected to achieve is to detect features which are salient because they realize categorical expectations if these features are frequent or evenly dispersed over the instances of a category. For example, the *peripeteia* or the *anagnorisis* in a tragedy can be noticed by readers because these features meet the readers’ expectations concerning typical features of tragedies. Empirical studies that are bound to a salience-based conception of distinctiveness will in most cases rely on this latter and positive connection between salience and distinctiveness. If a specific candidate measure *f* is supposed to detect distinctiveness in a qualitative sense, the respective sense of distinctiveness needs to be specified to this latter form of salience based on accordance with typical

8 The ›key‹ metaphor (Bondi 2010, 4 f.) misleadingly suggests that keyness measures possess the general capacity of identifying salient features, because key words are salient and because keyness measures detect key words. As long as the capacity of detecting salient features is not proved empirically based on evaluation studies, this assumption lacks evidence.

genre features. Section 4 will show the relevance of this conceptual distinction for the process of evaluation a candidate measure and hence for integrating it to qualitative reasoning.

The example of typical genre features such as *peripeteia* or *anagnorisis* for the category of tragedies leads us to the second distinction, which we shall call the discrepancy between reception category and word features. Features that are perceived by readers in a text and regarded as typical to the category the work is perceived in, are usually features of a more or less complex and composed shape, for example, a specific plot structure, the inclusion of a certain type or role of fictional character (such as the detective in crime fiction) of a motive, form, topic, theme, metric, or rhyme. As words usually are entered as input to the candidate measures of distinctiveness, distinctiveness appears on both levels, on the level of complex features in a qualitative sense and on the level of word features in terms of a quantitative candidate measure. This gap between word and complex features must be bridged based on sophisticated evaluation strategies which in turn have to be based on the previously clarified concept of distinctiveness.

4 Evaluation and Operationalization

Various concrete uses of the concept of distinctiveness can be located in the three-dimensional space we outlined in the third section. Any such use can be operationalized by a specific quantitative candidate measure if that measure is evaluated with regard to the specific, corresponding qualitative concept of distinctiveness. This in turn necessitates designing an evaluation scenario. We confine ourselves to the two most common and most important combinations, firstly, a relativist, agnostic taxonomic interest, and, secondly, a relativist, salience-based hermeneutic interest.

4.1 Taxonomic Systems and Classification Tasks

A relativist, agnostic and taxonomic interest is widespread in computational literary studies and digital genre stylistics. We have to start by asking in which case such an interest is successfully fulfilled by an operationalized procedure. According to reconstructions in general genre theory, this type of task is – in its most radical form – based on the following first two axioms:

1. The entire literary field is a hierarchical system of classes, where all subclasses are subsets of their parent class and where all classes on each horizontal level are mutually exclusive.
2. Every document *D* can be assigned to one and only one class on each horizontal level.

This taxonomic concept of distinctiveness is perfectly operationalized if a candidate measure fulfills both axioms. In computational genre stylistics, where measures of distinctiveness are applied, a less radical idea of distinctiveness can be found that has a slight tendency toward a historical interest. This strategy can be characterized by a third and additional rule:

1. The system of categorization for literary genres or other types of literary categories shall correspond to the practices, the semantics, and the conventions of categorization that were established in the historical culture that shall be investigated.

Here, the extension of each category is predefined and given by metadata information. At this level, measures of distinctiveness can come into play. The most immediate evaluation strategy is a classification task in the framework of hierarchical multi-class supervised machine learning. Features that are identified as distinctive by a specific candidate measure are given as input features to a classification algorithm. The evaluation can be based on accuracy scores for assigning texts to their original categories based on the input features. This strategy can be of significant epistemic value. For categories that are known in advance to be sound and distinct categories, the interaction of measures of distinctiveness and supervised learning algorithm can confirm that there must be a textual basis for the distinctness between the genres or other types of categories that were introduced according to rule (III). However, at this point, the scope of epistemic value is exhausted as long as the procedure remains agnostic with regard to the interpretability of the features. There is nothing wrong with such an axiomatic and agnostic approach as long as there is no need to bring the results back to any qualitative understanding of interpretable categorical features such as genre features articulated in historical genre poetics. This interpretability is, however, what we actually aim at.

4.2 Evaluating a Salience-based Approach on the Level of Aboutness

Evaluating the idea of distinctiveness for a hermeneutic and salience-based interest requires to bridge the gap between the level of word features, which are processed by measures of distinctiveness, and the level of complex features, which are perceived as distinctive by readers. Only complex features of specific reception categories are likely to correlate with word features at all. Structural properties or character networks, on the level of plot, for example, are not likely to be good candidates to correlate with word frequencies. Research on keyness measures often has in mind two kinds of complex features to be expressed statistically: style and theme (Scott 1997; Egbert/Biber 2019). Theme usually is modeled based on a more technical concept of aboutness. We will concentrate on operationalizing and evaluating

distinctiveness on the level of aboutness because it is less complex and raises less methodological challenges than the other levels including that of style. The basic structure, as it is offered by Ryle (1933, 10) is:

1. Document *D* is about *q*.⁹

As Ryle already pointed out, *q* can be a noun or a proposition *p*. Information retrieval, which has provided the most thorough methodological elaboration of aboutness, operationalizes *q* on the level of index terms, which are mostly nouns:

1. Document *D* is about index term *w* of a query (cf. Bruza et al. 2000, 1).

For operationalizing search engine queries and similar tasks in information retrieval, this structure may be satisfactory. If this structure could be directly transferred to literary studies, things would be easy, because aboutness could be directly expressed by distinctive word features and the gap between complex features and word level would not arise. At first glance, aboutness claims appear on the word level as expressed in (ii) also in literary studies: claims that a literary work is about love, crime, sex, drugs, or war, are customary. However, there may be love stories where the word ›love‹ occurs rather seldom or not even once. If a work is said to be about love, then we expect one of several plot structures that realize the fulfillment of a, commonly, initially hindered love. Distinctiveness on the level of aboutness within the field of genre research is mostly represented in a propositional structure. The variable *q* in (i) is a sentence or a whole description, for example, when we claim that detective fiction is about restoring social order by solving a crime, whereas the education novel is about the intellectual and social development of the protagonist. Thus, we prefer the following basic structure with a proposition *p* instead of a single term at the position of *q*:

1. *D* is about *p*.

Remarkably, the level of word features does not show up in this basic structure but can be included as we build our trust in the application of measures of distinctiveness upon the expectation that aboutness claims of the form (iii) correlate with the frequency or distribution of a series of words.¹⁰ **[10]** Thus, we can combine sentences (i), (ii), and (iii) to articulate the following sentence:

9 We regard each document *D* in a corpus as an instance of a work, according to the concept of work as it is used, for example, by Walton (1970).

10 See Scott (1998), Warren (2010), who operationalizes aboutness in terms of word n-grams, Gabrielatos (2018) and Egbert/Biber (2019).

1. Based on the frequency, distribution and/or dispersion of a series of words w in D , it can be inferred (in a probabilistic and non-conclusive way) that D is about p .

As we already pointed out, we do not expect that this inferential structure can be applied for candidate measures of distinctiveness in order to detect complex structural features such as *anagnorisis*, *peripeteia*, or specific types of character networks. It is promising only with regard to the level of theme. While the level of word features is based on statistical and relative distinctiveness in the second dimension (see section 3.2), complex features can be expected to be distinctive either in a relativist sense or as *differentia specifica* depending on the context of hermeneutic interest in the first dimension (see section 3.1). Therefore, there can be use cases where a complex feature that is expected to be distinctive for a genre or another type of category as *differentia specifica* shall be translated to (or represented as) word features that are distinctive in the relativist and statistical sense that is characteristic of quantitative procedures. Moreover, salience (in the wide sense of perceptibility in the third dimension from section 3.3) only applies to the level of the propositional aboutness claims (iii). The level of the frequency distribution of word features is supposed to be agnostic, in contrast. The actual challenge is, therefore, to proceed from the level of salient aboutness claims to the agnostic level of the frequency and distribution of word features. The relationship between the output of a measure of distinctiveness and the proposition p within the aboutness claim has to be proved empirically. As we have shown in section 2 for the relationship between the concept of keyness and keyness measures, this relationship, which is expressed in (iv), cannot be covered by any candidate measures unless it is evaluated successfully. The keyness metaphor (see note 8) can lead to a fallacy as it suggests that a feature with such statistical properties gives us insight into a document in the following form: (1) Any word that is identified as key or distinctive in a candidate measure is either a proper noun, or a function / stop word, or a content word (for example a substantive, verb, adjective, or adverb) (Baker (2004)). (2) Content words which are key to a text are indicators of the aboutness of that text whereas function words are indicators of the style of that text (Egbert/Biber 2019). The latter assumption (2) is fallacious, because there can be content words that are identified by a candidate measure and that do not amount to the aboutness of a text. There is no analytical or logical connection between a keyness measure and aboutness. It is only the metaphorical sense of the word ›key‹ which misleadingly suggests such a substantial content-based connection between feature and text. Hence, this relationship has to be established independently of these measures. It can be modeled with reference to the hypothetico-deductive method as it was introduced to hermeneutic reasoning by Føllesdal (1979). Firstly, a hypothetical and deductive aboutness indication

thesis with an if–then–syntax has to be generated, with the aboutness claim in the if-clause and with the expected word features in the then clause:

1. If D is about p , the words w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n are characteristic to D .

This relation of w 's being ›characteristic to D ‹ is abstract. It can be either a salient or an agnostic relationship. In either case, it cannot be accessed directly but only in indirect ways. The fact that there is no established gold standard for evaluating keyness (see section 2) and *a fortiori* for candidate measures of distinctiveness implies that there is not yet any accepted procedure that facilitates directly correlating propositional aboutness claims with the perception of characteristic words, so that there is not yet any procedure that enables us to justify theses of the form (v). Different workarounds for an agnostic conceptualization of word features are conceivable. These workarounds would have to yield an abstract evaluation dictionary that combines an aboutness claim with word features $\{p: w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n\}$. Such an evaluation dictionary could, for example, be based upon extracting summaries of texts in literary histories, or on quantitative procedures such as topic modeling (Blei 2012). As we aim at a concrete solution for the task of triangulating candidate measures of distinctiveness with a qualitatively meaningful concept of distinctiveness, we do not go into more detail for agnostic workarounds because we do not see any viable path towards qualitative interpretability based on completely agnostic workarounds. This does not, however, entail that such a path does not exist.

Instead, we favor a salience-based strategy that models the relationship between the propositional aboutness and agnostic frequency and distribution of word features in such a way that not only the propositional aboutness claim, but also the word features and hence the relationship between both have to be salient. In the strategy we favor, empirical reader response analysis and our analysis of the concept of salience in the context of poetics of rules versus aesthetics of deviation come into play. The most straightforward way to design a reader response evaluation study for this scenario is to prime readers' expectations on propositional aboutness claims. The initial question which can be posed to the participants who read document D is: ›Given that the story of D is about p , which words are salient as indicators of that aboutness?‹ With this initial question, the reading process of each participant is framed by a categorical expectation, that of the somewhat artificial aesthetic category of (hereinafter referred to as *about- p -texts*). This framing transforms the attention of readers and thus the perception of words. Words that are initially inconspicuous to readers can become salient, i.e. become features indicative of a category. By this strategy, the ambiguity of salience that we proved in section 3.3 can be dissolved and

specified exactly to the sense of perceived distinctiveness that is in principle detectable by candidate measures and that is in the aesthetic interest of detecting distinctive genre features according to historical genre semantics as elaborated in section 3.1. This evaluation strategy will prove successful if the following conditions are fulfilled:

1. The agreement between the participants must be sufficiently high. If the agreement is low, this strategy fails for a specific document and the associated aboutness claim.
2. The agreement rate in (1) must not be achievable without directing readers' attention to the propositional aboutness claim. The strategy (1) would turn out to be unnecessarily complicated if the same (or a higher) rate of agreement would be achieved independently of priming the reading process with the categorical expectation of propositional aboutness. In this case, our central thesis of the proposition-based – instead of a term-based – structure of aboutness claims would be weakened.
3. The results have to be generalized on the level of text groups. The interagreement must be high for all texts of that artificial category of *about-p-texts*. At this stage, the logic of *differentia specifica* from section 3.2 has its rationale. The artificial class is composed exclusively of texts which are about p but not of texts which are not about p . If this step is successful, it can be transformed to a generalized reader response dictionary that assigns aboutness propositions p to n words with the form $\{about-p-texts: w_1, w_2, \dots, w_i\}$ (with $n = i$). This dictionary will serve as the basis for evaluation.
4. In the final step, candidate measures come into play. If the conditions (1) to (3) are fulfilled (or based on a dictionary as extracted in the previous example for an evaluation task), the different candidate measures can be ranked with regard to the extent of matching word features for the artificial class of *about-p-texts* compared to a comparison class. For each candidate measure, the distinctive features for that class compared to the contradictory class of *not-about-p-texts* is generated as a candidate measure dictionary with the same form $\{about-p-texts: w_1, w_2, \dots, w_j\}$ (with $n = j$). This dictionary is then compared to the evaluation reader response dictionary from the previous step (3) with regard to the degree of mutual concordance between features w_i and w_j and based on evaluation metrics such as, for example, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

A candidate measure with acceptable performance in step (4) can justifiably be called a measure of distinctiveness and be used in real-world scenarios, for example for text groups that were assigned to different genres in historical literary culture. Here, it can serve to test whether a specific aboutness

assumption that has been evaluated qualitatively in advance is valid for texts of a ›real‹ genre G . The stronger the concordance of the results for G with that of the artificial category of *about- p -texts*, the stronger the evidence that being about p is a distinctive feature of the historical genre G . Probably, from step to step between (1) and (4), we will lose interagreement and concordance.¹¹ [11] As candidate measures of distinctiveness do not possess any inner sense of propositional aboutness, we have to prepare ourselves for rather low matching rates between reader response and statistical output.

If a hermeneutic interest shall be pursued, distinctiveness has to be conceptualized and operationalized as salient distinctiveness in the sense that has been clarified in section 3 and operationalized based on designing an evaluation scenario in this section. On at least one level in the process of modeling a qualitatively meaningful understanding of distinctiveness, features have to be conceptualized as salient features. In our exemplary scenario, this is the level of propositional aboutness claims. This salience-based level has then to be correlated to the presumably agnostic level of the frequency of words. We have proposed a salience-based framework of reader response analysis. Of course, all evaluation strategies can fail empirically, and in some or even many cases they certainly will. However, as we clarified the conditions of failure and thus the conditions of success, this is, from an empirical perspective, the most promising solution.

5 Conclusions and Consequences

We summarize our theses and results and draw further methodological conclusions. Our central thesis is that triangulating the quantitative and the qualitative perspective can only be achieved by means of a double strategy: Firstly, that of clarifying the concept that shall be operationalized in a qualitative way, and, secondly, that of designing an evaluation scenario that articulates justifiably expectable results of the previously clarified concept. So far, existing studies on keyness measures are as reductionist as Carnap's model of explication, instead of being integrative. We maintain that establishing an integrative model requires, in the first instance, a clarification of the qualitative meaning of the underlying concept. And it requires, secondly, an evaluation of a quantitative procedure with regard to a qualitative understanding. We did not find any contribution that tried to undertake this second task of evaluation. Unless both tasks are performed, the meaning of ›measure of keyness‹ or ›measure of distinctiveness‹ can only be expressed in mathematical terms, but not in qualitative terms. We contend that evaluation,

¹¹ The issue of low interagreement and concordance rates between reader response and statistical output has its counterpart in information retrieval. Maron (1977) introduced an operationalization of the degree of satisfaction a user has when assigning an index term to a document as the predicate ›R-about‹ (cf. Bruza et al. 2000).

as we have described it, is a constitutive part of justifying and thus clarifying the qualitative sense of a concept. Without such an evaluation, we do not know whether a candidate measure detects features that are distinctive in the precise sense of distinctiveness that we have in mind.

We have limited ourselves to designing two evaluation scenarios for the most common uses of the concept of distinctiveness in computational literary studies within the three-dimensional space of possible uses: firstly, a taxonomic interest based on an agnostic and frequentist understanding of distinctiveness, and, secondly, a historical and hermeneutic interest. Although classification offers an evaluation strategy that is appropriate for an axiomatic interest, this agnostic handling of distinctive features is not suitable to be interpreted in a qualitative way. Here, we can return to Carnap's idea of the sciences from the second section. His idea is normatively dominated by the primacy of his understanding of contemporary physics in the 1930s. Hence, the third requirement is essential to him: »The explicatum is to be a fruitful concept, that is, useful for the formulation of many universal statements« (Carnap 1950, 7). This requirement would be appropriate for an autonomous world of universal laws which could be labeled the ›sciences of natural laws of literature‹. A radical strategy of establishing taxonomic systems, independently of historical concepts, can be understood as a part of such a nomothetic enterprise. Our model of a qualitative clarification of the concept of distinctiveness would, in principle, allow for such a hegemonic understanding of computational literary studies, but we do not advocate approaches of that kind. Quite the contrary, our discussion has shown that such kinds of enterprises would be isolated and not be able to gain insight either into historical processes or into the aesthetic qualities of literary works.

With regard to the common limitation of candidate keyness measures as merely exploratory tools, we advocate a more critical and deliberate use of the notions ›explanation‹, ›interpretation‹ and ›exploration‹. We agree that whenever evaluation fails, we can still use keyness measures in an exploratory manner on the level of discovery. And we admit that exploratory use is widespread and still widely acknowledged in digital humanities research. There is nothing wrong with exploration, as long as we do not claim this exploratory use to be an interpretation of the output in any epistemologically ambitious sense. What can reliably be done with exploration is to consider the output, return to the texts and to reinterpret these texts by giving special attention to the words that are delivered by a candidate measure. In the specific case of taxonomic evaluation, subsequent to a systematic, agnostic and relativist validation of the concept of distinctiveness, an exploratory use of measures of distinctiveness with regard to individual word features can be highly valuable. For genres that are well known in literary studies, and

that can be replicated by means of classification tasks based on features that are detected as distinctive by a candidate measure, we can extract these features in order to reinterpret our philological knowledge of the distinctness between these concrete genres. Once again, however, it is the text but not the output of the candidate measure that can directly be interpreted. Subsequent to and independent of exploration, justification must then be based on philologic text analysis or other epistemologically established procedures. This paper, however, aimed to overcome the limitations of exploration by preparing the ground for explanatory technical procedures in the context of justifying philological hypotheses on distinctiveness, based on the notion of salience.

This paper offered an operationalization of a salience-based use of the concept of distinctiveness by evaluating distinctiveness on the level of aboutness. Hence, the question remains how further reception categories of distinctive salient features could be operationalized. In this respect, we recommend modesty: For features such as plot structure, the candidate measures are not likely to be a promising technique at all. The most promising level next to aboutness may be that of style. However, for that level, some new and intricate troubles arise: If a specific qualitative form of style – such as *Kanzleistil* (officialese) in early 18th century – shall be described, a qualitative expectation of that form must be articulated, in the same way a specific propositional aboutness claim is to be articulated. One problem is that such qualitative descriptions of different styles are less consensual, less standardized, and often rather metaphorical in literary studies (Toolan 2014). If, however, stylistic analysis is meant in the way it is applied in authorship attribution, stylistic features are modeled as agnostic features from the outset. Here, the path towards a qualitative interpretation is obstructed. For this reason, we are afraid that the area of aboutness is the only promising reception category for applying measures of distinctiveness.

The most general methodological implication of our discussion for literary theory in general is that triangulation can only be realized individually, but not universally. As qualitative research in the social sciences cannot be equated to hermeneutic work in literary studies, and as styles of reasoning are, among each other, highly contrary and often contradictory in literary studies, it is clear that any idea of a uniform qualitative paradigm would be absurd. This entails that each qualitative use of the concept of distinctiveness has to be specified through a concrete rationale. In our evaluation scenario, it is that of empirical reader response analysis, which in turn borrows fundamental assumptions on categorical expectations, and which is located in a very specific aesthetic interest. Other and completely different forms of rationale may be viable, but there has in each case to be one concrete rationale because there is no trivial bridge from salient distinctive features (on the level of propositional aboutness claims) to the

agnostic frequency and distribution of word features which are computed by statistical candidate measures. This fundamental structure of the problem of integrating a quantitative procedure to a qualitative understanding implies that no candidate measure of distinctiveness that proved to be successful in this or another respect can be regarded as a universally applicable tool for analyzing distinctiveness in literary studies in general. This is why the integration of computational procedures into literary studies cannot be achieved by a general methodological demonstration but only by numerous specific integrations.

References

- Baker, Paul, Querying keywords. Questions of Difference, Frequency and Sense in Keyword Analysis, *Journal of English Linguistics* 32:4 (2004), 346–359.[10.1177/0075424204269894](https://doi.org/10.1177/0075424204269894)
- Blei, David M., Probabilistic Topic Models, *Communications of the ACM* 55:4 (2012), 77–84.[10.1145/2107736.2107741](https://doi.org/10.1145/2107736.2107741)
- Bondi, Marina, Perspectives on Keywords and Keyness. An Introduction, in: Marina Bondi/Mike Scott (eds.), *Keyness in Texts*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia 2010, 1–18.[10.1075/scl.41.01bon](https://doi.org/10.1075/scl.41.01bon)
- Bruza, P.D. et al., Aboutness from a Commonsense Perspective, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science* 51:12 (2000), 1090–1105.[10.1002/1097-4571\(2000\)9999:9999::AID-ASH1026>3.0.CO;2-Y](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4571(2000)9999:9999::AID-ASH1026>3.0.CO;2-Y)
- Burrows, John, ›Delta‹: a Measure of Stylistic Difference and a Guide to Likely Authorship, *Literary and Linguistic Computing* 17:3 (2002), 267–287.[10.1093/lc/17.3.267](https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/17.3.267)
- Burrows, John, All the Way Through: Testing for Authorship in Different Frequency Strata, *Literary and Linguistic Computing* 22:1 (2007), 27–47.[10.1093/lc/fqj067](https://doi.org/10.1093/lc/fqj067)
- Carnap, Rudolf, *Logical Foundations of Probability*, Chicago/London/Toronto 1950.
- Da, Nan Z., The Computational Case against Computational Literary Studies, *Critical Inquiry* 45 (2019), 601–639.[10.1086/702594](https://doi.org/10.1086/702594)
- Duncker, Axel, Gattungssystematiken, in: Rüdiger Zymner (ed.), *Handbuch Gattungstheorie*, Stuttgart/Weimar 2010, 12–15.
- Egbert, Jesse/Doug Biber, Incorporating Text Dispersion into Keyword Analyses, *Corpora* 14:1 (2019), 77–104.[10.3366/cor.2019.0162](https://doi.org/10.3366/cor.2019.0162)
- Firth, John Rupert, The Technique of Semantics, *Transactions of the Philological Society* (1935), 36–72.[10.1111/j.1467-968X.1935.tb01254.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-968X.1935.tb01254.x)
- Fish, Steven, *Are Muslims Distinctive? A look at the evidence*, Oxford 2011.[10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199769209.001.0001](https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:osobl/9780199769209.001.0001)
- Fishelov, David, Genre Theory and Family Resemblance – Revisited, *Poetics* 20:2 (1991), 123–138.[10.1016/0304-422X\(91\)90002-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-422X(91)90002-7)

- Føllesdal, Dagfinn, Hermeneutics and the hypothetico-deductive method, *Dialectica* 33:3–4 (1979), 319–336. [10.1111/j.1746-8361.1979.tb00759.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1746-8361.1979.tb00759.x)
- Fricke, Harald, *Norm und Abweichung*, München 1981.
- Fricke, Harald, Definitionen und Begriffsformen, in: Rüdiger Zymner (ed.), *Handbuch Gattungstheorie*, Stuttgart/Weimar 2010, 7–10.
- Gabrielatos, Costas, Keynes Analysis: Nature, Metrics and Techniques, in: Charlotte Taylor/Anna Marchi (eds.), *Corpus Approaches to Discourse. A critical review*, Oxford 2018, 225–258. [10.4324/9781315179346-11](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315179346-11)
- Greene, Jennifer C., Is Mixed Methods Social Inquiry a Distinctive Methodology?, *Journal of Mixed Methods Research* 2:1 (2008), 7–22. [10.1177/1558689807309969](https://doi.org/10.1177/1558689807309969)
- Gries, Stephan Th., Dispersions and Adjusted Frequencies in Corpora, *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics* 13:4 (2008), 403–437. [10.1075/ijcl.13.4.02gri](https://doi.org/10.1075/ijcl.13.4.02gri)
- Gymnich, Marion/Birgit Neumann/Ansgar Nünning (eds.), *Gattungstheorie und Gattungsgeschichte*, Trier 2007.
- Hempfer, Klaus W., Zum begrifflichen Status der Gattungsbegriffe: Von »Klassen« zu »Familienähnlichkeiten« und »Prototypen«, *Zeitschrift für französische Sprache und Literatur* 120:1 (2010), 14–32.
- Herrmann, Berenike J./Karina van Dalen-Oskam/Christof Schöch, Revisiting Style, a Key Concept in Literary Studies, *Journal of Literary Theory* 9:1 (2015), 25–52. [10.1515/jlt-2015-0003](https://doi.org/10.1515/jlt-2015-0003)
- Jauß, Hans Robert, *Literaturgeschichte als Provokation der Literaturwissenschaft*, Konstanz 1967.
- Kelle, Udo, Die Integration qualitativer und quantitativer Forschung – theoretische Grundlagen von »Mixed Methods«, *Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie* 69:2 (2017), 39–61. [10.1007/s11577-017-0451-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-017-0451-4)
- Kilgariff, Adam, Comparing Corpora, *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics* 6:1 (2001), 97–133. [10.1075/ijcl.6.1.05kil](https://doi.org/10.1075/ijcl.6.1.05kil)
- Klimek, Sonja/Ralph Müller, Vergleich als Methode? Zur Empirisierung eines philologischen Verfahrens im Zeitalter der Digital Humanities, *Journal of Literary Theory* 9:1 (2015), 53–78. [10.1515/jlt-2015-0004](https://doi.org/10.1515/jlt-2015-0004)
- Lamping, Dieter, *Handbuch der literarischen Gattungen*, Stuttgart 2009.
- Lijfijt, Jeffrey et al., Significance Testing of Word Frequencies in Corpora, *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* (2014), 1–24. [10.1093/llc/fqu064](https://doi.org/10.1093/llc/fqu064)
- Lincoln, Yvonna S./Egon G. Guba, Paradigmatic Controversies, Contradictions, and Emerging Confluences, Revisited, in: Norman Denzin/Yvonna S. Lincoln (eds.), *Handbook of Qualitative Research*, Thousand Oaks, CA 2018, 108–150.
- Maron, M.E., On Indexing, Retrieval and the Meaning of About, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 28:1 (1977), 38–43. [10.1002/asi.4630280107](https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.4630280107)
- Müller, Ralph, Kategorisieren, in: Rüdiger Zymner (ed.), *Handbuch Gattungstheorie*, Stuttgart/Weimar 2010, 21–23.
- Paquot, Magali/Yves Bestgen, Distinctive Words in Academic Writing: A Comparison of three Statistical Tests for Keyword Extraction, *DIAL – Digital Access to Libraries*,

<https://dial.uclouvain.be/pr/boreal/object/boreal:76052> (17.09.2021), 1–23 (originally published in *Language and Computers* 68 [2009], 247–269).

Rácz, Péter, *Saliency in Sociolinguistics. A Quantitative Approach*, Berlin/Boston 2013. [10.1515/9783110305395](https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110305395)

Ryan, Marie L., Introduction: On the Why, What, and How of Generic Taxonomy, *Poetics* 10:2–3 (1981), 109–126. [10.1016/0304-422X\(81\)90030-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-422X(81)90030-9)

Ryle, Gilbert, About, *Analysis* 1:1 (1933), 10–12. [10.1093/analys/1.1.10](https://doi.org/10.1093/analys/1.1.10)

Schmidt-Hidding, Wolfgang, Zur Methode wortvergleichender und wortgeschichtlicher Studien, in: *Europäische Schlüsselwörter*, Vol. I: *Humor und Witz*, ed. by Sprachwissenschaftlichen Colloquium (Bonn), München 1963, 18–33.

Schröter, Julian, Gattungsgeschichte und ihr Gattungsbegriff am Beispiel der Novellen, *Journal of Literary Theory* 13:2 (2019), 227–257. [10.1515/jlt-2019-0009](https://doi.org/10.1515/jlt-2019-0009)

Scott, Mike, PC Analysis of Key Words – and Key Key Words, *System* 25:1 (1997), 1–13. [10.1016/S0346-251X\(97\)00011-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0346-251X(97)00011-0)

Scott, Mike, *WordSmith Tools Manual. Version 3.0*, Oxford 1998.

Šklovskij, Viktor, Die Kunst als Verfahren [1917], in: Jurij Striedter (ed.), *Russischer Formalismus*, München 1969, 5–35.

Stamatatos, Efstathios, A Survey of Modern Authorship Attribution Methods, *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology* 60:3 (2009), 538–556. [10.1002/asi.21001](https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21001)

Strube, Werner, Sprachanalytisch-philosophische Typologie literaturwissenschaftlicher Begriffe, in: Christian Wagenknecht (ed.), *Zur Terminologie der Literaturwissenschaft*, Stuttgart 1989, 35–49.

Stubbs, Michael, Three Concepts of Keywords, in: Marina Bondi/Mike Scott (eds.), *Keyness in Texts. Corpus Linguistic Investigations*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia 2010, 21–42. [10.1075/scl.41.03stu](https://doi.org/10.1075/scl.41.03stu)

Swales, John, *Genre Analysis. English in Academic and Research Setting*, Cambridge 1990.

Toolan, Michael, The Theory and Philosophy of Stylistics, in: Peter Stockwell/Sara Whiteley (eds.), *Handbook of Stylistics*, Cambridge 2014, 13–31. [10.1017/CBO9781139237031.003](https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139237031.003)

Tukey, John W., *Exploratory Data Analysis*, London et al. 1977.

Underwood, Ted, *Distant Horizons. Digital Evidence and Literary Change*, Chicago 2019. [10.7208/chicago/9780226612973.001.0001](https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226612973.001.0001)

Vofßkamp, Wilhelm, Gattungen als literarisch-soziale Institutionen, in: Walter Hinck/Alexander von Bormann (eds.), *Textsortenlehre – Gattungsgeschichte*, Heidelberg 1977, 27–44.

Walton, Kendall L., Categories of Art, *Philosophical Review* 79:3 (1970), 334–367. [10.4324/9781315303673-102](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315303673-102)

Warren, Martin, Identifying Aboutgrams in Engineering Texts, in: Marina Bondi/Mike Scott (eds.), *Keyness in Texts*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia 2010, 113–126. [10.1075/scl.41.09war](https://doi.org/10.1075/scl.41.09war)

Williams, Raymond, *Keywords. A Vocabulary of Culture and Society* [1976], revised edition, New York 1983.